

**PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO THE
STUDY OF THE TRIAD-N·C·S- PART XI. OXIDATION OF
PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDE WITH COPPER SULPHATE,
CUPRIC CHLORIDE, COPPER NITRATE, FERRIC
CHLORIDE AND IODINE.**

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Copper sulphate and cupric chloride have been found to be reduced by phenylthiocarbamide in acid medium with the simultaneous formation of complexes of the reduced salts. The reaction consists of two stages, primary and secondary. Primary reaction is independent of temperature, concentration of the reactions and dilution of the medium; the secondary change is largely influenced by temperature and is attended with the complex formation.

The present communication records an examination of the unexpected phenomenon observed by Lal and Krall (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 477) that copper sulphate oxidises phenylthiocarbamide producing Hector's base (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1176).

The action of oxidising agents has often been studied (for references *vide J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 31). The general course of the reaction is as follows;

The present investigation has established that the reaction with copper sulphate or cupric chloride can be subdivided into primary and secondary changes. The primary change which consists in the reduction of the cupric salt to cuprous state by phenylthiocarbamide which itself undergoes oxidation to Hector's base is according to the general equation given above. Our experiments have shown that this change is independent of a change in the dilution of the medium, of concentration of the reactants and of temperature, but it takes place only in an acidic medium, the inherent acidity of the aqueous solutions of above copper salts being enough for the purpose. The secondary change which is largely influenced by temperature, takes place simultaneously with the primary one or closely

follows it, and consists in the formation of insoluble complexes of unchanged phenylthiocarbamide with the cuprous salts giving mostly $(\text{Ph.Thi})_2 \cdot \text{Cu}_2\text{SO}_4$ and $(\text{Ph.Thi})_2 \cdot \text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_2$ at ordinary temperatures and $(\text{Ph.Thi})_2 \cdot \text{Cu}_2\text{SO}_4$ and $(\text{Ph.Thi})_2 \cdot \text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_2$ at 100° . Amounts of copper in the complexes obtained at different temperatures agree with the composition of the compounds above described. Cupric salts do not themselves combine with phenylthiocarbamide. But in acidic media they oxidise a part of phenylthiocarbamide to Hector's base and the cuprous salts, so produced, immediately begin to combine with the unchanged phenylthiocarbamide to form insoluble complexes. This removal of phenylthiocarbamide as insoluble complexes acts as a limiting factor on the extent of the oxidative change. The nature of the complexes formed is influenced by temperature and so the temperature affects the net result of the changes in as much as that for every two molecules of cuprous sulphate formed either six or twelve of phenylthiocarbamide are removed in the form of complex. This is supported by the fact that previously prepared cuprous chloride forms a complex with phenylthiocarbamide in a quantitative manner.

It has been shown (Lal and Krall, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 477) that silver nitrate combines with phenylthiocarbamide to form an insoluble complex and possibly it is the insolubility of this which prevents any oxidation-reduction in the case of silver nitrate.

Ferric chloride has been found to oxidise phenylthiocarbamide to Hector's base, itself undergoing reduction to colourless FeCl_2 . No complex appears to be formed in this case as the solution becomes colourless and shows only the turbidity due to precipitated sulphur on standing, but no bulky complex is precipitated and the reduced salt can be completely precipitated as Prussian blue with potassium ferricyanide.

Copper nitrate in aqueous solutions and aqueous iodine in acidic media have also been found to oxidise phenylthiocarbamide to Hector's base. These reactions are proposed to be investigated in further detail.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Copper Sulphate and Cupric Nitrate.—Known amount of phenylthiocarbamide was dissolved in water or the desired medium at the required temperature and dilution. A solution of copper sulphate (20%) was at once added and the mixture vigorously stirred. In the experiments conducted with solutions heated to boiling point the flame was removed after the addition of copper sulphate solution.

TABLE I.

Ratio of the reactants Ph ₂ Thi:CuSO ₄ (r/soth mole)	Dilution (c.c.)	Medium	Temperature	Copper sulphate.		SO ₄ ²⁻ used up for complex formation.	Atomic ratio in which Cu & SO ₄ are utilised for complex formation.	Hector's base expected to be formed as calculated on reduction.	Hector's base formed.	Percentage of initially present Ph ₂ Thi oxidised to Hector's base (cal- culated on reduction).	Percentage of Cu in complex.	Remarks.	
				Copper present.	Copper used up for complex formation.								
1:1	275	Pure aqueous	95°-100°	1:2558.	1:896g.	0:4210g.	213:100	0:65	0:63g.	21.1	17.66	These figures correspond to the formation of the complex (Ph ₂ Thi) ₂ Cu ₂ SO ₄ with small quantities of the other complex (Ph ₂ Thi) ₂ SO ₄ mentioned below.	
1:2/3	"	"	"	0:8467	1:2787	0:4447	196:100	0:65	0:62	23.3	17.6		
1:1/2	"	"	"	0:6254	0:9442	0:4540	208:100	0:63	0:60	23.5	17.51		
1:26/100	"	"	"	0:5932	0:8658	0:4249	210:100	0:61	0:61	22.7	17.5		
1:23/100	"	"	"	0:2974	0:4493	0:2134	211:100	0:395	0:26	22.7			
7:4	"	"	"	0:7172	1:6836	0:6134	208:100	0:64	0:595	23.8	17.8		
2:3	"	"	"	1:9065	2:1248	0:4512	208:100	0:64	0:585	23.8	17.95		
1:2	"	"	"	2:5015	3:777	0:6175	227:100	0:64	0:59	23.8	17.6		
1:4	"	"	"	5:028	7:5930	0:6230	196:100	0:68	0:58	25.3			
1:1	120	"	"	1:2714	1:9200	0:5856	196:100	0:61	0:58	22.8	17.2		
1:1	700	"	"	1:2714	1:9200	0:5936	211:100	0:65	0:52	23.3	17.6		
1:1	330	"	40°	1:2714	1:9200	0:3764	200:100	0:40	0:43	14.6	11.96		These figures correspond to the formation of the complex (Ph ₂ Thi) ₂ Cu ₂ SO ₄ chiefly.
1:1	450	"	20°	1:2714	1:9200	0:3630	200:100	0:39	0:43	14.2	11.58		
1:1	900	"	8°	1:2714	1:9200	0:3494	200:100	0:37	0:38	13.7	11.13		
1:1	250-275	N-H ₂ SO ₄	95°-100°	1:2714		0:6016		0:63	0:595	23.5	17.6		A black residue of sulphides of copper is obtained and Ph ₂ NH ₂ CN is formed to the extent of 30% approximately. (Ph ₂ Thi) ₂ Cu ₂ Cl ₄ is formed.
1:1	"	N/10-H ₂ SO ₄	"	1:2504		0:5944		0:625	0:62	23.2			
1:1	"	N-NH ₂ Ac	"	1:2743		1:2714		nil	nil			A black residue of sulphides of copper is obtained and Ph ₂ NH ₂ CN is formed to the extent of 30% approximately. (Ph ₂ Thi) ₂ Cu ₂ Cl ₄ is formed.	
1:1	"	N-NaAc	"	1:2714		1:2714		nil	nil				
1:1	100	Conc. HCl	80°-85°	1:2714	1:9200	0:8314	nil	0:87	0:73	32.45	23.9		

TABLE I (Continued)

Ratio of reactants Ph. Thi: CuCl ₂ (x/50th mole).	Dilution.	Medium.	Temperature.	Copper chloride		Copper used up for complex formation.	Cl ₂ used up for complex formation.	Atomic ratio in which Cu & Cl ₂ are used for complex formation.	Hector's base expected to be formed as calculated on reduction of CuCl ₂ to CuCl.	Hector's base formed.	Percentage of initially present Ph. Thi. oxidised to Hector's base.	Percentage of copper in complex.	Remarks.
				Copper present.	Cl ₂ present.								
"	250c c.	Aq. Neutral	95°-100°	1.2664g.	0.7339g.	0.7339g.	0.4148g.	1:1	0.77g.	0.73g.	28.7	21.7	A mixture of complexes (Ph.Thi) ₂ Cu ₂ Cl ₂ and (Ph.Thi) ₃ Cu ₃ Cl ₃ is formed.
"	"	" N-HCl	"	1.2714	0.7123	0.7123	0.4148	1:1	0.75	0.75	28.0	21.7	
"	"	" Aq.	"	"	0.7711	0.7711	0.4148	1:1	0.81	0.73	30.0	21.7	
"	45°	Neutral	"	"	0.7290	0.7290	0.4148	1:1	0.76	0.70	28.3	21.1	
"	150	"	"	"	0.7474	0.7474	0.4148	1:1	0.79	0.72	29.4	21.5	
"	45°	"	70°	1.3119	1.465	0.6475	0.3690	1:1	0.68	0.58	25.4	17.7	The complex (Ph.Thi) ₂ Cu ₂ Cl ₂ is chiefly formed.
"	330	"	40°	"	"	0.6339	0.3598	1:1	0.668	0.63	24.9	16.6	
"	450	" N/10 HCl	20°	"	"	0.6339	0.3598	1:1	0.668	0.614	24.9	16.6	
"	700	"	40°	"	"	0.6338	0.3598	1:1	0.668	0.634	24.9	18.6	
"	900	" Aq	48°	"	"	0.6204	0.3396	1:1	0.655	0.604	24.4	18.9	
"	100	Conc. HCl	80°-85°	1.2714	0.8341	0.8341	0.3396	1:1	0.88	0.73	31.8	23.91	Complex (Ph.Thi) ₂ Cu ₂ Cl ₂ is formed.
Ph. Thi: CuCl ₂ (x:1)	50	"	"	1.2841	1.2367	1.2367	0.3396	1:1	nil	nil	nil	23.93	

* The figures indicate that copper sulphate in the form of Cu₂SO₄ combines with phenylthiocarbamide. The quantities of Hector's base formed correspond to the copper reduced. More than one fourth of phenylthiocarbamide initially present is never oxidised to Hector's base. When temperature is changed a different complex is formed.

The mixture was allowed to cool to the room temperature and filtered. The complex was collected, washed, and dried at 100°-110°. The filtrate was treated with an excess of 10% ammonium hydrate solution, when on standing Hector's base granulated out. It was filtered, dried on a water-bath, and weighed on a tared filter. The copper and SO₄ were estimated in the filtrate as usual.

Copper in the complex was determined in oven-dried samples at 100°-110°, known weights of which were ignited and subsequently dissolved in concentrated nitric acid.

Copper nitrate gave similar results.

The results are given in Table I.

Cupric Chloride.—Chloride ions were estimated in the liquor by Volhard's method and copper determined as usual.

Ferric Chloride.—Phenylthiocarbamide (1.52 g.) was dissolved in boiling water (100 c.c.) and to the solution was added an equivalent of boiling ferric chloride solution. The yellow colour of the ferric chloride at once disappeared. After some time sulphur was deposited in the form of fine white powder. The solution was filtered and treated with an excess of potassium ferricyanide solution when an intense blue bulky precipitate of Prussian blue was obtained. It was filtered and from the clear yellow filtrate Hector's base was precipitated with ammonium hydrate, and identified through its m.p. and acyl derivative.

Iodine.—Aqueous iodine solution was gradually run into an acidified hot solution of phenylthiocarbamide. It became decolourised as soon as added and a pale yellow colouration developed when an excess was run in. The solution was filtered and from the filtrate Hector's base was precipitated as usual with aqueous ammonia. The reaction can probably be represented by the following equation :

